

The role of low carbon fuels towards net-zero in integrated assessment models and energy system models: A critical review

Zipeng Liu^{a,b,1,*}, Meixi Zhang^{a,c,1}, Christian Bauer^{a,**}, Russell McKenna^{a,b}

^a Laboratory for Energy Systems Analysis, Centers for Nuclear Engineering and Sciences and Energy and Environmental Sciences, Paul Scherrer Institute, PSI, 5232, Villigen, Switzerland

^b Chair of Energy Systems Analysis, Institute of Energy and Process Engineering, ETH Zurich, Zurich, 8092, Switzerland

^c Climate Policy Lab, Department of Environmental Systems Science, ETH Zurich, Zurich, 8092, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

Low-carbon fuels (LCFs) are crucial for achieving net-zero CO₂ emission goals in integrated assessment model (IAM) and energy system model (ESM) scenarios. The absence of a standardized LCF classification system and inconsistencies in modeling approaches have obscured the integration of various LCFs within these models and makes a meaningful comparison of scenario outcomes difficult. This study addresses these issues by conducting a comprehensive critical review of the representation of LCFs in IAMs and ESMs, focusing on the fuel's role in shaping net-zero emission futures. We categorize LCFs into key groups, including electrification, hydrogen, synfuels, and biofuels. Our analysis reveals substantial gaps in technical modeling, lifecycle emissions data, incomplete modeling of environmental impacts beyond CO₂ emission, and discrepancies in LCF applications across sectors. To enhance the accuracy of future scenarios, we recommend adopting a unified LCF classification system, standardized input data, and more detailed sectoral applications. Additionally, we advocate for the integration of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) into IAMs and ESMs to improve the evaluation of LCFs' full environmental impacts, providing a more comprehensive foundation for net-zero emission pathways.

1. Introduction

The urgent need to limit global warming to 1.5 °C or 2 °C is increasingly pressing, as the window of opportunity for achieving these targets rapidly closes [1]. This challenge is underscored by the record high of 36.8 gigatons (Gt) of CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion and industrial processes in 2022 [2]. Accelerating the global energy transition is critical not only to meet climate goals but also to enhance long-term energy security and achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [3]. Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) and Energy System Models (ESMs) are indispensable tools for exploring and optimizing pathways to these climate objectives [4,5].

Modeling outcomes from IAMs and ESMs consistently highlight the necessity of phasing out fossil fuels while deploying a range of new technologies. A significant focus of these models is on the pivotal role of end-use electrification powered by renewable energy [3,6,7]. However, for sectors where electrification is not viable, the role of low- and zero-carbon fuels (LCFs) becomes crucial. The growing interest in LCFs such as biofuels, hydrogen, and power-to-X fuels reflects their potential to decarbonize hard-to-electrify sectors. Although LCFs have been the

subject of extensive techno-economic analyses [8–11] and environmental Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) [12–14], their integration into IAMs and ESMs has not kept pace with technological advances.

A significant challenge in modeling LCFs is the lack of a unified definition, with existing models often employing ambiguous criteria [15,16]. The classification of fuel as “low carbon” is contingent upon its life cycle greenhouse gas (GHG) emission factor (EF), which varies based on factors such as energy inputs, raw material sources, production methods, and application sectors [17]. While LCAs are crucial for accurately calculating these EFs [15], their application in identifying LCFs within IAMs/ESMs remains limited [18]. For the purpose of this paper, we define LCFs as fuels with the potential to achieve low, zero, or negative GHG emissions over their entire life cycle, including their end-use. This category encompasses fuels with no direct GHG emissions in end-use (e.g., electricity, hydrogen, ammonia) and hydrocarbons produced from biomass, carbon capture and utilization (CCU), direct air capture of CO₂ (DAC), or recycled fossil wastes, provided they are powered by renewable or low-emission electricity.

Many LCF technologies are still in the early stages of development, introducing uncertainty and hindering their systematic representation

* Corresponding author. Laboratory for Energy Systems Analysis, Centers for Nuclear Engineering and Sciences and Energy and Environmental Sciences, Paul Scherrer Institute, PSI, 5232, Villigen, Switzerland.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: zipeng.liu@psi.ch (Z. Liu), christian.bauer@psi.ch (C. Bauer).

¹ These authors contributed equally to this work.

in models [19]. As the future decarbonization of energy systems heavily relies on these emerging technologies, the accuracy and comprehensiveness of their inclusion in current models are crucial for identifying sustainable zero-carbon emission pathways [6].

Previous studies have reviewed the roles of specific LCFs, such as hydrogen [6,20,21], synfuels [19], and biofuels [22–24], in IAMs or ESMs. For example, Bolat and Thiel [25] analyzed the integration of hydrogen energy systems in seven ESMs, proposing a hydrogen supply chain architecture that included hydrogen production and delivery pathways, though only five blue hydrogen production options were considered. Hanley et al. [26] provided a comprehensive review of the role of hydrogen in low carbon pathways and scenarios across global, regional and national ESMs. They produced the timeline of the emergence of hydrogen in these models and identified the main drivers of hydrogen, highlighting its varying importance across different scenarios. Li et al. [27] reviewed existing studies on optimization models regarding hydrogen supply chain network design, emphasized the need for sustainability analysis of hydrogen energy transformation. Blanco et al. [20] proposed a taxonomy with nine hydrogen archetypes to classify energy models that included hydrogen, in which the only archetype considering environmental and high spatial resolution aspects is the ESMs integrated LCA. Quarton et al. [21] explored the inconsistency of hydrogen's role in these models, while the scope was limited to 12 models used in global reports from influential institutions. Sorrenti et al. [19] examined the role of power-to-X (PtX) fuels in hybrid renewable energy systems, and the role of biofuels has been discussed separately in several ESMs [22–24].

In general, previous studies primarily focus on the technical and economic roles of hydrogen and mature biofuels in a limited number of models, employing varying methods of model selection and offering only a partial analysis from model structure to scenario outcomes. In many cases, critical discussions of environmental assessment and emission factors of these LCF are lacking, resulting in an incomplete picture of their contribution to net-zero pathways. To our knowledge, no up-to-date review comprehensively covers the entire LCF portfolio as represented in IAMs and ESMs.

Given the rapid evolution of LCF technologies and the increasing complexity of IAMs and ESMs, a comprehensive review that systematically evaluates the full LCF portfolio and their representation in these models is needed. This study systematically examines how LCFs are incorporated into IAMs/ESMs, emphasizing their production pathways to ensure a detailed understanding of their techno-economic and environmental implications. By doing so, our work identifies potential inconsistencies in model structures, differences in scenario assumptions, and limitations in lifecycle impact integration, all of which influence the projected role of LCFs in future energy systems. Through this analysis, we offer insights into how LCF modeling can be improved to provide a more robust basis for net-zero scenario development.

To achieve this, we combine a systematic literature review of the representation of LCF in IAMs and ESMs with a comparative analysis of modeling structures and scenario outcomes. We first establish a database of IAMs and ESMs that include LCFs, categorizing them based on technological detail, geographical coverage, and sectoral integration. Next, we analyze scenario outputs from the IPCC AR6 database and other leading energy models not included there, assessing the representation of electrification, hydrogen, synfuels, and biofuels under various climate policy settings. Our study focuses particularly on inconsistencies in technology coverage, cost assumptions, scenario setting and lifecycle emissions treatment, which are often overlooked in previous reviews. Building on gaps identified, we propose strategies for improving the integration of LCA data into IAMs and ESMs, ensuring that the environmental trade-offs and benefits of LCFs are more comprehensively reflected in net-zero transition pathways.

The contributions of this study are as follows.

- We provide a comprehensive review of how LCFs are currently incorporated in the selected IAMs and ESMs, highlighting existing ambiguities in definitions, system boundaries and modeling approaches.
- We propose a categorization of LCF technologies based on production pathways and feedstock used (low-carbon electricity, biomass, and natural gas), ensuring alignment with key decarbonization strategies.
- We provide a detailed techno-economic and environmental characterization of LCFs as represented in IAMs/ESMs, and recommend strategies for improving LCA integration with these models.
- We analyze scenario outcomes and explore how model differences and scenario assumptions influence the projected roles of LCFs in achieving net-zero emissions.

We identify critical modeling gaps and propose best-practice recommendations to enhance the transparency, consistency and accuracy of addressing LCFs in IAMs/ESMs. By refining the problem definition and focusing on the technological integration of LCFs, this study fills an important gap in the literature. Our findings not only provide a clearer picture of how LCFs are represented in IAMs/ESMs but also serve as a foundation for improving scenario-based analyses that inform net-zero policies and energy strategies.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the methodology used to investigate the representation and role of LCFs in ESMs/IAMs. Our approach is structured into three main components: Section 2.1 presents a comprehensive literature review and systematic model selection process. Section 2.2 focuses on a detailed scenario analysis to evaluate the role of LCFs in various decarbonization pathways. Section 2.3 explores the scope and structure of the review, outlining the boundaries of our investigation and how the different components of the study are interconnected.

2.1. Literature search and model selection

Scopus and Web of Science are explored for our literature search. Search items were generated for IAMs/ESMs and specific LCF technologies, such as 'Integrated assessment models', 'energy system models', with key terms for LCFs (TITLE-ABS-KEY ("low carbon fuel" OR "renewable fuel" OR "alternative fuel" OR "sustainable fuel")). The literature search covered a temporal period from January 1, 2005, to March 31, 2024. This search strategy enabled us to capture the increasing body of research on LCF technologies and their representation in IAMs/ESMs, as depicted in Fig. 1 (left).

In our model selection process, we categorized energy models based on various criteria, including modeling approach (computational, mathematical, physical), technological detail (bottom-up vs. top-down), and disciplinary focus: IAM, ESM, and CGE (computational general equilibrium) model [28]. While CGE models are widely used in energy transition research for policy decision-making, their representation of technology is often approximated through production functions due to their macroeconomic focus [29], which limits the detailed exploration of LCFs. ESMs, on the other hand, offer a bottom-up, technology-oriented representation of energy systems, using dynamic optimization and simulation frameworks for energy and climate policy appraisal. IAMs typically integrate an energy system model with a macroeconomic model, a climate model, and other components, providing a more comprehensive representation of LCFs across multiple domains.

To evaluate the modeling of LCFs and their role in energy transition scenarios, we prioritized models with a high degree of technological detail, a system-wide scope, and a long-term horizon. These selection criteria narrowed our focus to specific ESMs and IAMs most relevant for energy system analysis.

We developed a filtering system to select IAMs and ESMs that align

Fig. 1. (left) Overview of the annual number of published articles and citations that include a type of LCFs and IAM/ESMs in their abstract, title or keywords. Data from Web of Science. And (right) the model selection process of IAMs/ESMs.

with our study objectives. As illustrated in Fig. 1 (right), the process begins with creating a model database from five sources. After removing the duplicate models and outdated versions, we apply two filters: first, ensuring the models had a technology-rich energy sector, and second, confirming the inclusion of at least one LCF technology and its application within the model. The scope of our analysis primarily focuses on global and multi-regional models to facilitate global and regional scenario analysis. To better understand model structures and compare different regional models, we also included three representative national ESMs, such as the R2X model, which incorporates detailed PtX technologies [30]. Table 1 provides an overview of these selected models, including their structure, geographical coverage, time horizon, spatial resolution, solution method, and key references.

2.2. Scenario analysis

Scenarios in IAMs/ESMs serve as narratives that describe plausible

future developments based on different assumptions about policies, technological advancements, and socioeconomic trends. These scenarios are crucial for exploring the potential impacts on the development of emissions, energy use, and other critical variables. To assess the role of LCFs in different scenarios, we conducted a quantitative analysis of scenario datasets generated by IAMs/ESMs, focusing on net-zero emission scenarios.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) AR6 database provides a comprehensive and relatively consistent categorization of IAM scenarios. Dekker et al. [54] analyzed the IPCC AR6 scenarios across nine IAMs using Sobol decomposition and identified the impact of three main drivers on scenario outcomes: climate targets, model characteristics, and scenario assumptions. They found that model characteristics – such as whether and how individual renewable and CCS technologies are represented – drive variation in scenario outcomes reflecting intrinsic uncertainties about long-term developments and possible mitigation strategies. However, they did not further explain

Table 1

Summary characteristics and methodologies of selected IAMs/ESMs. Structure – HY: hybrid, BU: bottom-up, TD: top-down.

	Structure	Geographical Coverage	Time Horizon	Spatial Resolution – number of regions	Solution method	Main References
AIM/Tech	BU	Global	2010–2150	33	Optimization	[31]
BET-GLUE	HY	Global	2010–2150	13	Optimization	[32]
COFFEE-TEA	HY	Global	2010–2100	18	Optimization	[33]
DNE21+	BU	Global	2000–2100	10	Optimization	[34]
EnergyPLAN	TD	Multi-regional, EU	A year	28	Simulation	[35]
EU-Calliope	BU	Multi-regional, EU	2018–2050	35	Optimization	[36]
GCAM	HY	Global	2015–2100	32	Recursive dynamic	[37]
GENeSYS-MOD	BU	Global	2015–2050	10	Optimization	[38,39]
GMM	BU	Global	2010–2100	17	Optimization	[40]
IMAGE	HY	Global	1970–2100	26	Simulation	[41]
JRC-EU-TIMES	HY	Multi-regional, EU	2010–2070	36	Optimization	[6]
MEDEAS	HY	Global	1995–2060	1	Simulation	[42]
MERGE-ETL	HY	Global	2015–2100	10	Optimization	[43]
MESSAGEix	HY	Global	2030–2110	11	Optimization	[44]
POLES-JRC	HY	Global	2015–2100	66	Recursive simulation	[45]
PRIMES	BU	Multi-regional, EU	2015–2070	30	Optimization	[46,47]
PROMETHEUS	HY	Global	2000–2100	10	Simulation	[48]
R2X	BU	Japan	A year	1	Optimization	[30]
REMod	BU	Germany	2000–2100	33	Optimization	[49]
REMIND-MAGPIE	BU	Global	2005–2100	6	Optimization	[50]
TEMOA-Italy	BU	Italy	2006–2050	1	Optimization	[51]
TIAM-ECN	HY	Global	2005–2099	36	Optimization	[52]
TIAM-UCL	HY	Global	2005–2100	16	Optimization	[53]

how model differences and scenario assumptions affect the scenario results for LCFs. Our study fills this gap by examining model structure and scenario assumptions, with a focus on net-zero scenarios involving LCFs across various application categories.

We first filtered the IPCC metadata indicators database [55] for models on our list that include net zero scenarios and passed the IPCC scenario vetting, ensuring that emissions and energy data were within reasonable historical ranges [56]. We then categorized the climate scenarios (C1 to C5) for each model and aggregated different versions of the same model, considering that structure changes are insignificant, allowing for meaningful aggregation of scenario outcomes [54]. The C1 to C5 categories focus on global temperature outcomes and are based on pathways that limit global warming to specific levels, such as 1.5 °C or 2 °C above pre-industrial levels. C1 scenarios focus on limiting warming to 1.5 °C, C2-C4 scenarios aim to limit warming to below or around 2 °C, and C5 scenarios allow warming to exceed 2 °C. The detailed definition of C1 to C5 categories can be found in Table S1.

For IAMs/ESMs not included in the IPCC AR6 database, we select scenarios from the most recent studies available, ensuring regional scope consistency and the inclusion of LCF applications. In cases where model studies lacked direct scenario data for LCFs, such as the EnergyPLAN [35] models' exploration of a 100 % renewable energy system for the EU, we noted the absence of detailed LCF output data. Since many ESM scenario designs are model-specific, with only a limited number of scenarios considering climate and net-zero targets, we could not obtain consistent LCF shares under the same scenario definitions across different models as for the models and scenarios present in the IPCC database. Therefore, for these models, we plotted the LCF share in 2050 for all scenarios within each model. The supporting information Excel

table provides a complete list of models and scenario protocols used in this study.

2.3. Scope and structure of our review

Fig. 2 illustrates the general structure of the LCF systems within the IAM/ESM modules considered in this review, detailing the flow of energy from resources through transformation and conversion processes to transport, storage, and final application. The diagram includes key resources such as renewables, wastes, natural gas, and nuclear energy, which feed into various transformation processes like electricity generation, hydrogen production (including green hydrogen and other types), synfuel production, and biofuel production. The outputs from these processes—such as electricity, hydrogen, methane, and hydrocarbon fuels—are then managed in the transport and storage phase before being distributed to electrifiable and non-electrifiable applications.

The diagram also integrates feedback loops that connect energy related GHG emissions to the environmental (primarily land use and climate) module and energy costs to the macroeconomic module. This highlights the interdependencies between energy systems, environmental impacts, and economic factors. To systematically assess the role of LCFs within IAMs, we introduce their representation step by step. We begin by examining synfuels within the ESM module, then analyze the impact of the LCF system through the emission, environmental, and economic modules. Finally, we compare the roles of the primary LCF categories across different ESMs/IAMs, assessing their contributions to emission reductions in the final scenario results.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the general representation of LCFs in ESM & IAM structures. The color-coded arrows distinguish between different types of flows. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

3. Results

In this section, we present the key findings from our review of LCFs in IAMs/ESMs. First, in Section 3.1, we provide an overview of the LCF technologies represented in various models, focusing on direct and indirect electrification, hydrogen, synthetic fuels, and biofuels. In Section 3.2, we analyze how LCFs are represented within energy system model structures, including the types of LCFs that have been modeled and their implementation. Following this, in Section 3.3, we examine the interactions between LCFs and the environment and climate modules of IAMs, with a particular emphasis on GHG emissions and environmental impacts, and assess the carbon accounting methods used for LCFs. Finally, in Section 3.4, we discuss the role of LCFs in the decarbonization scenario outcomes of IAMs/ESMs and explore the ratios of LCFs in sectoral applications of final energy demand.

3.1. Model overview and LCF framework

Table 2 provides a detailed comparative analysis of the key characteristics of the IAMs included in our review. It highlights essential attributes that influence the representation of LCFs in these models, including solution concepts, solution horizon, technology diffusion mechanisms, and technology learning data sources. The solution concept distinguishes between Partial Equilibrium (P) models, which focus on the energy sector in isolation while assuming other economic sectors remain unchanged, and General Equilibrium (G) models, which capture interactions between energy markets and the broader economy [20,57]. Technology diffusion mechanisms follow Logit Substitution (O) for gradual adoption based on cost competitiveness or Linear Choice (I) for deterministic adoption based on cost minimization. Additionally, the models are categorized based on their data inputs, indicating whether they utilize endogenous (Yellow) or exogenous (Green) technology learning data. The renewables section encompasses electricity production technologies and biofuels, along with detailed considerations of

application sectors, CO₂ and hydrogen grid infrastructure, and environmental impacts. This comparative framework facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the methodological diversity and focus areas of prominent IAMs in the context of energy system optimization and policy analysis.

Fig. 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the lifecycle and system framework of LCFs considered in our analysis, based on insights from the IAMs/ESMs we reviewed. This framework encompasses primary energy sources, fuel production technologies, and key fuel categories, including hydrogen, ammonia, liquid hydrocarbon fuels (e.g., biodiesel, bio-kerosene, diesel, kerosene), and carbon-based gases (e.g., biogas, methane). The main fuel categories are further connected to transportation and storage infrastructures, as well as end-use applications across various sectors. While energy transport and storage are critical components of the LCF system infrastructure and are discussed in our analysis, our primary focus is on the role of LCF's production technologies and application sectors. Particular attention is given to the transport sector, detailing road transport, long distance trucks, shipping, and sustainable aviation fuels (SAFs) for aviation. By systematically integrating fuel production, distribution, and utilization pathways, this framework ensures a holistic representation of LCF systems for robust techno-economic and sustainability assessments.

3.2. Representation of LCFs in IAMs/ESMs

In this section, we aim to provide an overview of the extent to which LCFs are represented in the selected models in terms of the technologies deployed and the feedstock used. As summarized in Table 3, we observe a split between models that cover conventional liquefaction based on fossil fuels (coal and natural gas) and models that focus on low-carbon synthetic fuels based on hydrogen and biomass. Most IAMs do not consider hydrogen-based synthetic fuels, neglecting the potential contribution of hydrogen-based synthetic fuels for decarbonization. PRIMES, which has been extensively used to construct the baseline in

Table 2

Overview of shortlisted model frameworks in this review. In the renewables resolution indicators, the number of renewable electricity or biofuels technologies considered in the models is indicated. The "Meaning" column shows the examples of corresponding indicators. Note that some models use different categories, such as in the BET-GLUE model, in which the industry application sector is categorized as "high temp process, low temp process, other electricity use, ...". In this and other similar cases, the number is noted as the number of subsectors the model included.

Name and version	Indicators	AIM/Tech 2.0	BET-GLUE 1.6-3.2	COFFEE-TEA 1.1	DNE21+	EnergyPLAN 16.2	Euro-Calliope 1.0	GCAM 7.0	GENESYS-MOD v3.0	GMM 1.0	IMAGE framework 3.2	JRC-EU-TIMES	MEDEAS-W	MERGE-ETL 6.0	MESSAGE-GLOBIOM 1.0	POLES-JRC	PRIMES 2022	PROMETHEUS 1.0	R2X	REMod	REMIND-MAgPIE 4.1	TEMOA-Italy 2.0	TIAM-ECN 1.1	TIAM-UCL 4.1.1	Meaning
Basic information	Solution concept	P	G	G	P	P	P	G	P	P	P	P	G	G	G	P	P	P	P	P	G	P	P	P	P: Partial equilibrium, G: General equilibrium; Yellow: fixed demand, Green: closed economy, Blue: price elastic demand M: myopic (recursive dynamic), F: foresight (intertemporal optimization) Technology diffusion: O: logit substitution, I: linear choice; Technology learning data: Yellow: endogenous data, Green: exogenous data
	Solution horizon	M	F	F	F	M	F	M	F	F	M	F	M	F	F	M	F	M	M	F	F	F	F	F	
Renewables resolution	Tech. learning & development	O	I	I	I	O	O	I	I	O	O	I	O	I	I	O	O	O	O	O	I	I	I	I	RE technology numbers: Bio w CCS; Solar (central PV, distributed PV, CSP); Wind (onshore, offshore); Hydro; Ocean; Waste Number of biofuel technologies considered from the LCF list
	Renewable electricity	7	5	8	8	8	7	7	8	8	7	8	8	8	7	8	7	7	7	7	5	4	5	8	
Application sector resolution	Biofuels	2	4	4	2	7	4	6	3	7	1	6	6	5	4	6	10	5	0	3	1	3	1	5	Space heating; Space cooling; Cooking; Refrigeration; Washing; Lighting (Water heating; Clothes drying; Other electrical/non-electrical uses) Freight trains; Heavy duty vehicles; Freight ships (Gasoline/Hybrid/Fuel-cell HDVs) Passenger trains; Buses; Light Duty Vehicles (LDVs); Electric/Hydrogen/Hybrid/Gasoline/Diesel LDVs; Passenger aircrafts; Electric Buses/Three-wheelers; LPG/CNG LDVs) Steel/Aluminium/Cement/Petrochemical/Paper/Plastics/Pulp production
	Residential & commercial	8	10	6	0	2	6	7	5	1	6	6	1	1	2	3	6	4	2	4	5	6	3	9	
	Freight transportation	4	3	4	0	1	4	2	3	1	4	4	4	1	1	3	3	1	3	5	2	3	4	3	
	Passenger transportation	9	5	8	0	3	7	14	9	6	9	7	2	1	0	9	9	6	1	7	3	5	8	5	
	Industry	3	6	3	0	1	7	3	7	1	3	7	7	1	0	3	7	2	3	4	3	6	4	6	
Grid infrastructure	International aviation	X					X					X	X			X						X			X: included
	CO ₂			X	X		X		X	X				X	X	X	X		X	X		X	X	X	
Environmental impacts	Hydrogen	X			X		X	X	X	X	X			X	X		X	X	X	X		X	X	X	CO ₂ fossil fuels; CO ₂ cement; CO ₂ land use; CH ₄ energy; CH ₄ land use; CH ₄ other; N ₂ O energy; N ₂ O land use; N ₂ O other; CFCs; HFCs; SF ₆ ; PFCs A: Agriculture, D: energy Demand, S: energy Supply, I: Inequality, E: Economic output, C: built Capital
	GHGs	1	2	9	5	5	1	13	2	1	13	1	6	13	12	12	1	4	0	2	13	1	8	13	
	Climate change impacts on:							AD	D		AIS	D	DE	SD	EC	D	SD								

Fig. 3. Complete overview of the LCF energy system framework identified in IAMs/ESMs with the coverage of LCF technologies identified in red boxes. Abbreviations: AEC: alkaline electrolysis cell, PEM: proton exchange membrane, SOEC: solid oxide electrolysis cell, HTE: high-temperature electrolysis, SMR: steam methane reforming, ATR: auto thermal reforming, CLR: chemical looping reforming, ASU: air separation unit, DAC: direct air capture, CCS: carbon capture and storage, HB: Haber-Bosch, RWGS: reverse water gas shift, SR: solar reforming, ST: solar thermochemical, FT: Fischer-Tropsch, BtG/L: biomass to gas/liquid, PtG/L: power to gas/liquid, StL: solar to liquid, RCF: recycled carbon fuel, DME: Dimethyl ether, LNG: liquefied natural gas, SAF: sustainable aviation fuel. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 3

The table displays the liquefaction feedstock and technologies on the left and the model names on top. For each technology the model represents, the corresponding table cell is crossed. The temporal resolution is indicated through the green color gradient. The lighter the green the higher the temporal resolution of the respective technology. From darkest to lightest color, the temporal resolution is categorized as annual, seasonal, weekly, day and night and hourly respectively.

Conversion Technologies: Liquid Fuels	TEMOA Italy	PRIMES	JRC-EU-TIMES	MESSAGEix	GCAM	TIAM-ECN	GMM	COFFEE	IMAGE	POLES	MERGE-ETL	GENESYS-MOD	BET-GLUE	IMACLIM-R	REMIND-MAGPIE	MEDEAS	PROMETHEUS	DNE21+	ReMOD	TIAM-UCL	EnergyPLAN	Calliope	AIM/Tech	R2X	WISEE	Temporal Resolution
	Coal	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Natural gas	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Seasonally
Biomass	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Weekly
Coal w/ ccs	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Day/Night
Natural gas plant w/ ccs	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Hourly
Biomass w/ ccs	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Hourly
Green Hydrogen	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Hourly

the EU Reference Scenario, covers all the liquefaction technologies. Models based on the TIMES framework has also increasingly incorporated not only the production technologies of LCFs but also their connection to respective end uses and carbon accounting. In the study of Blanco et al., JRC-EU-TIMES was expanded that hydrogen was connected too all end-use sectors beyond the transport sector. On the other hand, the study of TEMOA Italy [51] expanded the technologies to evaluate an alternative emissions accounting method specifically for the TIMES framework.

Other models, particularly those on the right side of Table 3, such as

ReMOD, Calliope, AIM/Tech, and R2X, tend only to include low-carbon e-fuels. These models are more interested in e-fuels' flexible role rather than their role in system decarbonization. These models also have higher temporal resolution to capture the degree of flexibility.

Table 4 shows that hydrogen, serving also as feedstock for e-fuel production, is covered by all models. 75 % of the evaluated models include biomass gasification and electrolysis for hydrogen production indicating that modelers consider hydrogen as a prominent energy carrier for system decarbonization. Gas steam reforming closely follows the low-carbon pathways as the conventional technology commercially

Table 4

The table displays the hydrogen production technologies on the left and the model names on top. For each technology the model represents, the corresponding table cell is crossed. The row of data at the bottom indicates the percentage of hydrogen production technology options each model represents. The column of percentage on the right indicates the extent this technology is represented by the models.

Hydrogen Production technologies	AIM/Technology	BET-GLUE	COFFEE-TEA	DNE21+	EnergyPLAN	Sector-Coupled Euro-Calliope	GCAM	GENESYS-MOD	GMM	IMAGE	JRC-EU-TIMES	MERGE-ETL	MESSAGE-GLOBIOM	POLES-JRC	PRIMES	PROMETHEUS	R2X	REMIND	TEMOA-Italy	TIAM-ECN	Technology Coverage
Gas steam reforming	x		x				x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x		60%
Gas steam reforming with CCS	x		x							x		x	x	x	x	x		x	x		50%
Ethanol steam reforming											x								x		10%
Solar methane reforming														x							5%
Coal gasification	x		x	x			x			x	x	x	x	x				x	x		55%
Coal gasification with CCS	x	x	x							x		x	x	x				x	x		45%
Coal partial oxidation															x	x			x		15%
Coal partial oxidation with CCS															x	x			x	x	20%
Biomass gasification	x		x	x			x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	75%
Biomass gasification with CCS	x		x						x	x		x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	60%
Biomass pyrolysis															x	x			x		15%
Oil partial oxidation															x	x			x		15%
Oil partial oxidation with CCS															x	x					10%
Electrolysis from grid/dedicated plant	x		x	x	x	x	x		x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	75%
Solar thermal thermolysis										x		x		x	x	x					25%
Nuclear thermal thermolysis														x	x	x					15%
Model Representation	44%	6%	44%	19%	6%	6%	25%	0%	19%	44%	31%	50%	44%	63%	63%	63%	6%	38%	69%	25%	

used for industries, such as refineries, at 60 %. Negative emission technologies (NET) such as Biomass Gasification with CCS (BECCS) serve as a popular Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) method. Unlike the modeling of synthetic and biofuels, technologies which has exhibit lower technology readiness have also been considered in models to test their contribution to decarbonization, such as nuclear thermal thermolysis at 15 % and solar methane reforming included by POLES.

It is worth noting that modeling documentation often does not specify which type of electrolyzer they use. The cost differences among Alkaline Electrolysis Cells, Alkaline Electrolyte Membranes, Polymer Electrolyte Membranes and Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cells remain substantial [58]. Furthermore, the biomass feedstock for biomass gasification often remains generic and unclear, whether it is from lignocellulosic crops, forestry, wood waste, agricultural residues, or municipal solid wastes. Differentiating the feedstock could result in overestimating the resource potential, considering not only the physical resource potential but also the policy regulations on which biomass feedstock qualifies.

Accurately representing the cost of capital (CoC) in ESM is critical for evaluating the economic feasibility and investment attractiveness of LCFs [59]. Renewable energy technologies, which are typically more capital-intensive than fossil fuels, show leveled cost of energy (LCOE) with high sensitivity to CoC variations. Misrepresentation of CoC can lead to inaccurate cost assessments and suboptimal policy decisions. Differentiated CoC rates, reflecting technological, geographical, and temporal risks, provide a more precise economic analysis [59]. For instance, CoC for European onshore wind projects varies significantly between countries. Incorporating realistic, risk-adjusted discount rates rather than uniform or social discount rates in IAMs enhances the accuracy of model outcomes [60]. This rigorous approach ensures that the models better capture the financial impacts of environmental policies and support the deployment of LCFs in achieving sustainable, low-carbon energy systems.

3.3. Representation of LCFs in IAMs: interactions with the environment and climate modules

Environment module. The environment module in IAMs models the impact of energy production and consumption on the atmosphere, land, and water bodies. This includes emissions of GHGs and other pollutants, as well as land-use changes associated with biomass supply for bioenergy production and renewable power generation. While LCFs generally offer climate benefits through reduced GHG emissions, they can also exhibit significant environmental trade-offs. For instance, biofuels, depending on their production methods, can have higher environmental impacts than fossil fuels, particularly in terms of land use, water consumption, and biodiversity loss [12]. Similarly, the land use required for renewable power generation infrastructure, such as solar and wind farms, can lead to habitat disruption and other ecological concerns [14].

IAMs simulate various scenarios to assess how different energy mixes can achieve climate goals while balancing these environmental factors. For example, they evaluate the potential of LCFs to contribute to improved air quality [61], optimized land use, and minimized environmental degradation, but also consider the risks associated with large-scale bioenergy production and the spatial demands of renewable energy technologies [62]. The implications of these simulations are crucial: while LCFs are necessary for decarbonizing hard-to-electrify sectors, their broader environmental impacts must be carefully managed to avoid unintended consequences [63].

To achieve model-specific analytical purposes, some IAMs combine energy-economic models with environmental modules of varying structures and focuses. The BET-GLUE model, for instance, integrates an energy-economic module with a bioenergy-land-use module to capture the complex interactions between bioenergy production and land-use-related CO₂ emissions. Geographically explicit land-use models are employed by several IAMs, such as MAGPIE, IMAGE, and GLOBIOM, to provide a more detailed regional representation. These models account for the regional variations in land use, which are critical when

considering the large-scale deployment of biofuels and renewable energy. For example, the GCAM model [64] enhances regional representation through agroecological zones, which helps to identify the specific environmental impacts of LCF deployment in different areas.

Another critical component of IAMs is the climate module, which links energy related GHG emissions to broader climate outcomes. IAMs calculate emissions from sectors such as energy production, transportation, land-use change, and waste, and these emissions are then integrated into climate models to project changes in atmospheric composition, radiative forcing, and temperature increases [65]. Models like REMIND, IMAGE, POLES, TIAM, and MESSAGE utilize the MAGICC climate model, which allows for the comparison of different GHG types and emission sources across scenarios. In contrast, GCAM employs the Hector climate model, which provides a more detailed consideration of carbon cycles within the atmosphere, land, and oceans.

While integrating environmental and climate modules with energy-economic models offers a more comprehensive understanding of the potential benefits and risks of LCFs, it also highlights the complexity of achieving sustainable energy transitions. The trade-offs associated with biofuel production, land use for renewable power, and the broader impacts on ecosystems and climate underscore the need for carefully balanced policies. These models inform decision-makers about the potential environmental costs of LCFs, encouraging the development of strategies that maximize climate benefits while minimizing environmental impacts.

Climate impacts and carbon accounting. In carbon/GHG emission accounting, ESM typically focus on reducing direct (on-site) CO₂ (or GHG) emissions during the operation of the technology under consideration. Direct emissions accounting emphasizes the emissions produced directly from energy generation processes, such as the combustion of fossil fuels in power plants [66]. Since ESM serve as the energy system components within many IAMs, all the IAMs model energy-related GHG emissions based on activity levels and emission factors.

As shown in Table 2, many IAMs with technology-rich energy systems primarily focus on the energy sector and CO₂ emissions, such as AIM/Tech, Calliope, MEDEAS, and PRIMISE. However, some IAMs with a broader scope extend their focus to include emissions from agriculture, land use, waste, and other human activities, such as MESSAGES-GLOBIOM, POLES, REMIND, and WITCH. These IAMs, which place a strong emphasis on environmental impacts, also tend to include a wider range of GHG emissions, including non-CO₂ gases [67].

The energy transition from conventional fuel supply to LCF systems will likely shift environmental impacts from the use phase to the manufacturing phase, which the primary emissions phase for renewable energy and storage technologies [68]. However, existing IAMs and ESMs have two deficiencies in modeling the GHG emissions of LCFs, particularly in terms of life cycle scope and the types of emission factors considered.

First, multi-sector emission modeling is often limited. While many models focus on emissions from the energy system, only a few incorporate comprehensive considerations of land use and other environmental impacts related to renewable energy sources. For instance, the GHG emissions associated with building wind turbines, solar panels, electrolyzers, and other infrastructure necessary for LCFs are typically represented within the industry sector in these models, but the detail and accuracy of this representation can vary significantly [69]. Biomass and crop supply-related GHG emissions should be captured by land-use modules, yet these are not always fully integrated or adequately modeled [70,71].

Second, non-CO₂ GHG emissions and other environmental impacts from these LCFs are often underrepresented. While carbon dioxide emissions receive significant attention, other critical emissions—such as methane leaks from natural gas supply chains, which can significantly influence the real emission factors of natural gas-based fuels—are not always fully accounted for [72]. Moreover, emissions and environmental burdens from the hydrogen life cycle [73,74], together with the

leakage of hydrogen which is increasingly recognized as having a climate impact due to its potential to interact with atmospheric chemistry and contribute to warming, are rarely considered in these models [26]. This omission is a significant gap, as hydrogen, biomass fuels, and synthetic fuels are often treated as carbon-free in the end-use sector, overlooking the emissions and environmental impacts that can occur at other stages of their life cycles.

Lifecycle emission accounting provides a more comprehensive approach by considering the entire lifecycle of energy technologies—from raw material extraction through manufacturing, operation, and decommissioning—to capture all associated emissions and broader environmental burdens [40]. Integrated scenario-based emissions accounting combines lifecycle and direct emissions accounting within comprehensive frameworks, using detailed energy, economic, and climate modules to simulate various policy and technology scenarios over time [75]. This approach enables the exploration of different pathways to achieve low-carbon futures, accounting for interactions between energy systems, technological advancements, and policy measures.

However, due to the lack of comprehensive LCA data [73], these approaches often require a combination of LCA with more traditional direct emissions accounting to accurately determine specific GHG emissions and environmental impacts in studies focusing on detailed emissions. The integration of LCA with IAMs/ESMs remains a challenge, but it is essential for accurately capturing the full spectrum of environmental impacts associated with emerging LCF technologies and pave the way towards comprehensively quantifying environmental externalities in economic terms, which could be integrated into optimization algorithms.

3.4. Representation of LCFs in IAM/ESM scenarios

Role of LCFs in the IPCC AR6 net-zero scenarios. After analyzing how LCFs are modeled in IAMs, the proportions of the main LCF categories in the current IAM scenario results in the final energy demand are visualized. Fig. 4 presents the share of electrification, hydrogen, and liquid bioenergy in final energy demand for 2030 and 2050 across five climate categories (C1 to C5) in IPCC AR6 net-zero scenarios from seven selected IAMs: COFFEE, GCAM, IMAGE, MESSAGE, POLES, REMIND, and TIAM. Each subplot focuses on a specific energy carrier and time frame. The data source is our model list included in the IPCC AR6 database; as described in the methodology section, seven models passed vetting, and the results of 405 scenarios are plotted.

In 2030, the share of electrification (top-left panel) shows relatively low and consistent values across all climate categories, with the majority of models reporting an electricity ratio below 0.3 across C1 to C5. However, notable variability is observed within individual models, particularly GCAM and REMIND, which show the highest variance across categories. Hydrogen shares (middle-left panel) in 2030 remain below 0.02 across most scenarios, reflecting the early stage of hydrogen deployment in decarbonization strategies during this period. The liquid bioenergy share (bottom-left panel) shows more prominence in C2 and C3 categories, particularly for the COFFEE model, where bioenergy shares exceed 0.1.

By 2050, the energy mix sees significant shifts. Electrification (top-right panel) becomes more dominant, particularly in C1 to C3 scenarios, where most models report ratios between 0.3 and 0.6, highlighting a marked increase in electrification. REMIND and IMAGE show the highest electrification ratios, particularly in the more stringent C1 and C2 categories. Hydrogen (middle-right panel) experiences substantial growth by 2050, especially in C1 to C3 categories, with ratios reaching 0.06 to 0.08 for several models, notably REMIND, TIAM, and IMAGE. The results indicate that hydrogen plays an important role in achieving net-zero emissions, especially in the most stringent climate scenarios.

For liquid bioenergy (bottom-right panel), the ratios in 2050 are more evenly distributed across categories, with COFFEE consistently

Fig. 4. Share of electrification, hydrogen, and liquid bioenergy in final energy demand in 2030 and 2050 across five climate categories (C1 to C5) in IPCC AR6 net zero reachable scenarios of seven selected IAMs.

showing higher shares across all categories. In particular, COFFEE leads in bioenergy use, with shares approaching 0.3 in C2 and C3 categories, while other models, such as POLES and REMIND, show smaller but notable contributions to liquid bioenergy, particularly in the transportation sector.

Overall, the data indicate that electrification and hydrogen become increasingly important components of final energy demand by 2050, especially in the more stringent C1 to C3 categories, while liquid bioenergy maintains a significant role in specific sectors and regions, particularly in models like COFFEE and POLES.

Role of LCFs in the sectoral energy demand. Fig. 5 presents the sectoral energy demand shares of electrification, hydrogen, and liquid bioenergy across the industry, transportation, and residential and commercial sectors for 2030 and 2050, under five climate categories (C1 to C5) based on IPCC AR6 net-zero scenarios. The analysis highlights notable variations in the modeling of LCFs across different sectors, with liquid bioenergy being represented solely in the transportation sector.

In the industry sector, the share of electrification remains relatively modest across all models in 2030, with most models reporting electricity shares below 0.4, even in the most ambitious climate categories (C1-C3).

However, by 2050, electrification becomes a dominant feature, particularly in the C1 to C3 scenarios, where several models, including REMIND and GCAM, report shares exceeding 0.6. This trend underscores the critical role of electrification in decarbonizing the industrial sector as climate targets become more stringent. Hydrogen usage in industry is minimal in 2030 across all models and scenarios, but by 2050, models such as REMIND and GCAM exhibit significant increases in hydrogen’s share, particularly in C1 and C3 categories, where hydrogen ratios in some scenarios exceed 0.08. This suggests that hydrogen will play a pivotal role in reducing emissions from energy-intensive industrial processes, especially in scenarios with aggressive decarbonization pathways. The GMM model accounts for the use of liquid bioenergy in industry, while only REMIND includes biogas in its industrial applications.

In the transportation sector, the share of electrification in 2030 is minimal across all climate categories and models, reflecting the continued reliance on conventional fuels in the near term. By 2050, however, electrification in transportation sees substantial growth, particularly in the C1-C3 categories, with models such as REMIND and IMAGE reporting electrification shares reaching 0.4. This shift indicates

Fig. 5. Sectoral energy demand shares of electrification, hydrogen, and liquid bioenergy in industry, transportation, residential and commercial sectors for 2030 and 2050, across five climate categories (C1 to C5) in IPCC AR6 net-zero scenarios from seven selected IAMs. Liquid bioenergy is shown only for the transportation sector due to limited data availability.

a strong movement towards electric mobility as part of the broader decarbonization strategy. The share of hydrogen in transportation also increases significantly by 2050. In particular, the IMAGE model predicts that hydrogen will account for nearly 30 %–40 % of transportation

energy demand in the C1 and C2 categories. This reflects hydrogen’s potential as a key decarbonization fuel in hard-to-electrify transportation modes, such as long-haul trucking and shipping. The use of liquid bioenergy remains a substantial component of transportation

Fig. 5. (continued).

energy demand throughout both 2030 and 2050, with the COFFEE model consistently showing the highest bioenergy shares. By 2050, COFFEE reports liquid bioenergy shares exceeding 0.3 in the C2 and C3 scenarios, making bioenergy a critical component of decarbonizing the transport sector. However, bioenergy shares vary widely across models, highlighting differing assumptions about feedstock availability, policy priorities, and technology deployment.

The residential and commercial sectors exhibit high levels of electrification even in 2030, with electricity shares above 0.4 in most models across all climate categories. By 2050, electrification dominates these sectors, with models such as GCAM and REMIND showing shares approaching 0.8 in C1 and C2 categories. This suggests that electrification will be the primary strategy for reducing emissions in residential and commercial buildings, particularly in scenarios with aggressive climate targets. Hydrogen use in the residential and commercial sectors remains limited across all models, with hydrogen shares not exceeding 0.035 by 2050. This indicates that while hydrogen may play a growing role in industry and transportation, its role in the residential and commercial sectors is likely to remain marginal.

Significant variations exist in how different models represent LCFs across sectors. For instance, models like COFFEE, IMAGE, and TIAM do

not include hydrogen use in the residential and commercial sectors, while POLES lacks detailed sectoral breakdowns for LCF categories. Additionally, some models have incomplete data for specific fuel applications; for example, TIAM-ECN does not provide bioenergy data, and TIAM-UCL omits hydrogen data for the transportation sector. Moreover, models such as GCAM and IMAGE fail to disaggregate bioenergy applications, limiting the ability to fully evaluate the role of bioenergy across diverse sectors.

In the transportation sector, most models, including MESSAGE and REMIND, account for biofuels in both passenger and freight transport. However, IMAGE exclusively models biofuels for freight transport, while others, such as POLES and TIAM, do not provide detailed data on transportation subsectors. Regarding aviation, although several models incorporate jet fuel production technologies within their energy systems, the data are often either unavailable or aggregated with synfuels, making it difficult to isolate aviation-specific results, as seen in Fig. S1.

Further details, including the year each scenario reaches net-zero emissions, the role of CCS, and average LCF ratios across models, are provided in the supporting Excel table.

Role of LCFs in literature based IAM/ESM scenarios. Table 5 summarizes the scenario data for non-IPCC IAM/ESM models, outlining

Table 5

Research specific scenario data collection of non-IPCC IAMs/ESMs. Abbreviations: ref: reference; Tech.: Technology; no.: number; Poli. Policy; Clim.: climate target; Envi: environmental; RE: renewable electricity; RES: renewable energy system.

Model and reference study for scenario analysis	Scenario development			Dimensions considered in scenario setting and scenario count								Available scenario results		
	Research aim	Scenario no.	Socioeconomic assumption	Technology dimension	Policy dimension	Climate target	Environment dimension	Tech.	Poli.	Clim.	Envi.	Scenario result data availability	Scenario result data time step	Scenario result LCF data
AIM/Tech [76]	Role of hydrogen-based energy carriers	22	SSP2	LCF technology availability: Default, CCSoff, LimBio, H2off, VRElowcost, H2lowcost	N.A.	500-1400 Gt CO2 budgets	N.A.	6	0	10	0	Supply and demand (data)	2005–2050, 5-year step	Hydrogen, Biomass, synfuel
BET-GLUE [32]	Role of end-use bioenergy technologies	18	SSP2	Availability of advanced end-use bioenergy and BECCS technologies: On/Off; None/full	Carbon taxes	1600, 1000, 400 Gt CO2 budges	Bioenergy supply limit	4	1	3	2	Supply (figure)	2050, 2100	Biomass, CCS
EnergyPLAN [35]	Transition to a 100 % renewable energy Europe	8	100 % renewable energy system	introducing renewable electrofuels	General consensus, heating policy	N.A.	N.A.	3	5	0	0	Supply (figure)	2050 ref	Energy supply (Biomass, RES, Waste)
EU-Calliope [36]	Technological and spatial diversity in a self-sufficient and carbon-neutral EU energy	411	EU ref	Renewable energy system	N.A.	Carbon neutral	N.A.	411	0	0	0	Supply and demand (figure)	2018 ref	Biofuel, electricity production, transport electrification
JRC-EU-TIMES [6]	Role of PtX in EU low carbon system	8	EU ref	CCS, PtL, hydrogen or biomass tech	N.A.	80 and 95 % CO2 reduction	N.A.	5	0	2	0	Supply and demand (figure)	2050 ref	Hydrogen, PtL, biomass
MEDEAS [42]	Transition to sustainable energy systems	4	SSP2	Energy source limitation	N.A.	N.A.	Climate change damage	2	0	0	2	Supply (figure)	1995-2100, yearly	Biomass, RES
PRIMES [77]	To ensure EU reaches climate neutrality by 2050	4	EU ref	Hydrogen, biofuel, electrification in transport system	Policy and market failures	Reducing net emissions by 90 % by 2040, net zero 2050	N.A.	0	4	0	0	Demand (figure)	2010–2050, 5-year step	Biofuel, electricity & hydrogen
R2X [30]	Flexible P2X technologies in a comprehensive energy system	2	IEA NZE scenario	P2X technology flexibility	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	2	0	0	0	Supply and demand (figure)	2019 ref	Hydrogen, synfuel
REMod [78]	Describe possible, consistent future developments	6	Germany reference	Technology change	Acceptance and sufficiency	Zero energy emission 2050	N.A.	2	3	2	0	Supply and demand (figure)	2030, 2050	Electrification, biomass, hydrogen, PtX
TEMOA-Italy [51]	Account for the LCF blending emission reduction	2	Italy ref	LCF blending share (hydrogen 6 %, syn-methanol 3 %, biodiesel 30 %)	N.A.	55 % reduction 2030, zero energy emission 2050 Italy	N.A.	1	0	0	0	Supply and demand (data)	2020–2050, 5-year step	Biofuel, hydrogen, synfuel

their research objectives, scenario assumptions (spanning technology, policy, climate targets, and environmental considerations), and the availability of scenario result data. Based on the available data, the share of LCFs in final energy demand across nine models is presented in Fig. 6. Among the models, AIM/Tech, BET-GLUE, GMM, PROMETHEUS, and GENeSYS-MOD are global, while the remaining models cover regional scopes, as indicated in the figure. As shown in Table 5, most of these models incorporate technology shifts and the adoption of specific LCFs within their scenario assumptions.

For the five global models, BET-GLUE shows relatively low overall energy demand and a limited contribution of LCFs compared to the others. AIM/Tech stands out with significantly higher levels of electrification and hydrogen use, while PROMETHEUS places greater reliance on biofuels. Notably, AIM/Tech is the only global model that includes hydrogen synthetic fuels in its scenario assumptions; in contrast, regional models tend to include synfuels more frequently, although they feature less scenario variation overall.

In terms of sectoral application, extracting normalized data for comparison across models proved challenging due to differences in how sectors and LCF types are accounted for, as well as the varying methods used for data aggregation. Issues such as double counting and vague separation of subcategories further complicate the comparison. For instance, AIM/Tech predicts that hydrogen will make up an average of 10 % of energy demand in the industrial sector and between 8 % and 20 % in the transportation sector, with an average of 16 %. The model also forecasts an average of 7 % of transport energy demand being met by hydrogen-based synfuels, alongside 8 % from biomass. JRC-EU-TIMES, another model providing detailed sectoral data, indicates that hydrogen demand in transport is twice that of its demand in industry applications.

4. Discussion

In this section, we analyze the key drivers and challenges affecting the role of LCFs in IAMs/ESMs, with a focus on their contribution to decarbonization scenarios. Section 4.1 explores the critical factors shaping LCF representation, such as model structure and scenario assumptions, and how these influence the modeling outcomes. In Section 4.2, we address the integration of LCA into IAMs/ESMs, highlighting existing research and methodologies. Section 4.3 identifies significant

barriers, including the limited inclusion of emerging LCF technologies, insufficient representation of environmental impacts, and the complexities of comparing results across models. Finally, Section 4.4 offers recommendations for future research to improve LCF modeling in energy transition pathways. We emphasize the need for enhanced temporal and spatial resolution, as well as greater transparency in model structures and data sources.

4.1. Drivers of the contribution of LCFs in decarbonization scenarios

Model structure. In IAMs, the share of hydrogen and biofuels in the IPCC scenario outcomes is mainly driven by model differences and then the climate targets of the scenarios [54] (Table S3). The first difference lies in the coverage of LCF technologies and the modeling resolution of the technology clusters. As shown in Fig. 4 and analyzed in section 3.3, the IMAGE model has the highest ratio of electrification in C1 to C3 category scenarios, with a particularly high and broad range of hydrogen applications by 2050. This is mainly due to the model's detailed hydrogen production sector, which includes electrolysis (PEM and SOEC) and SMR based hydrogen [79]. The IMAGE model also separately assumes global cumulative hydrogen production via different technologies and includes a detailed hydrogen application system, as shown in Table 2. However, these assumptions may lack precision as the volume is not based on renewable electricity, and the IMAGE model only has an annual resolution for electricity modeling. For the emerging of hydrogen energy, we found that by 2030, TIAM, REMIND, and POLES will introduce hydrogen energy earlier, especially in the C3 to C5 categories. REMIND considers electrolytic hydrogen production and the production of methanol and methane through hydrogen, including the extensive application of hydrogen energy in transportation, industry, and construction [65]. It also accounts for the learning-by-doing effect of these relatively new technologies to reduce costs and compete flexibly with existing technologies [65]. TIAM and POLES models share this advantage, unlike other models, COFFEE, and MESSAGE, that do not consider significant hydrogen energy applications.

Regarding biofuels, the COFFEE, POLES, and REMIND models predict a higher ratio of biofuel application in net-zero achievable scenarios compared to others, especially COFFEE. Previous comprehensive analyses of bioenergy technologies in multiple IAMs have shown that different models significantly impact the coverage of technologies and

Fig. 6. Share of electrification, hydrogen, synfuel, and biofuel in the total final energy demand, the total final energy demand, and the total share of non-e LCF (non-direct electrification LCF: hydrogen, synfuel, and biofuel) in selected ESM/IAM of all scenarios in 2050. If not specifically noted, the modeled region is the world.

their application in later stages of carbon reduction. For instance, models containing biogas, such as BET-GLUE, MESSAGE, REMIND, and COFFEE, tend to utilize it [80]. Bioenergy is also closely linked to CCS because CCS effectively enhances the emission reduction capacity of biofuels and turns them into carbon dioxide removal methods. Models that do not include hydrogen energy often rely on bioenergy. Under stringent climate targets, IAMs consistently rely on bioenergy and CCS [71].

Some IAMs do not include new alternative technologies, adhering to the precautionary principle that the most robust approach in uncertain contexts is to focus on technologies that are currently available and proven to be commercial. This is crucial given the urgent need to stabilize the climate and reverse current unsustainable trends. For example, IPCC models not included in Fig. 4, such as MEDEAS [42], only consider biofuels and do not include CCS, other negative emission technologies, or hydrogen.

The studies examined from the ESMs; BET-GLUE, PROMETHEUS and GENeSYS-MOD all display a low level of synfuel production and little variation. These models also only include fossil-fuel based synthetic fuels, hence indicating that fossil-fuel based synthetic fuels play a negligible role in the decarbonization of the energy system as these models do not represent any hydrogen-based synthetic fuel technology. On the other hand, models with comprehensive coverage of both hydrogen and synthetic fuel technology allow model flexibility to utilize these technologies. For example, TEMOA-Italy with the highest technology coverage in hydrogen production, 69 % (see Table 4), and synfuel technologies dominate in its final synfuel demand as well. There is little variation, though, in its results due to the limited scenario runs (see Table 5). Following this observation, JRC-EU-TIMES results also in a high level of synthetic fuel production despite a huge variation among the scenarios. Noticeably, AIM/Tech with a high temporal resolution also shows a high consumption of synthetic fuels with similar levels of hydrogen. Due to the dependency of green hydrogen-based synthetic fuels on renewable electricity, the modeling of intermittency of renewable energy becomes crucial in determining the extent of synthetic fuel production. The models with higher synthetic fuel demand are accompanied by a higher electricity demand, indicating the surge of renewable electricity needed to support this production. Finally, the proportion of bioliquid demand remains similar among the models, potentially due to similar resource constraints.

Scenario assumptions. Previous research [54] has suggested that scenario settings have a relatively low impact on energy variables within IAMs, as these models typically adopt consistent scenario settings, with many net-zero emissions scenarios based on SSP2. However, it is noteworthy, as shown in Fig. 4, that some SSP1 scenarios within the IMAGE model exhibit particularly high hydrogen usage rates (28 %–60 %). This highlights the influence of baseline and background data assumptions on the adoption of new fuels [81]. Certain IAMs have developed specific scenarios for emerging technologies. For instance, some scenarios in REMIND, POLES, and TIAM include considerations for low-carbon policies and renewable energy development, which align with their higher hydrogen usage outcomes. Since all the IAM scenarios we analyzed achieve net-zero emissions and are categorized by climate targets, LCFs exhibit competitive dynamics within different scenarios of the same model. We believe that scenarios with greater emphasis on future technological advancements and preferences can provide more accurate predictions regarding the types and roles of LCFs.

For ESMs, as illustrated in Table 5, scenario settings primarily encompass carbon reduction targets and compared to IAMs, are more focused on technology-based assumptions. According to Fig. 6 and Table 5, we found that models with assumptions considering LCF technologies in their scenarios generally show higher electricity dependency and LCF usage, such as AIM/Tech and R2X. Scenarios with stricter climate targets also require higher LCF shares to meet emission reduction goals. For example, REMod and TEMOA, which both aim for net-zero emissions by 2050, rely significantly on renewable electricity and

LCFs, respectively, to achieve these targets. REMod exhibits the highest dependency on renewable electricity, whereas TEMOA primarily depends on LCFs to reach net-zero emissions.

4.2. Integration of LCA with IAMs/ESMs

As mentioned earlier, LCA can provide more accurate emission factors and broader environmental impacts for ESMs and IAMs [82], enhancing their ability to LCF transitions comprehensively. This section synthesizes current research and methodologies that integrate LCA into IAMs and ESMs, particularly concerning LCFs. Several key studies exemplify the progress and limitations in this field. For example, Pehl et al. [7] integrated prospective LCA with global energy modeling to explore life-cycle emissions of future low-carbon power systems, though the focus was primarily on electricity and lacked sectoral differentiation across technologies. Similarly, Volkart et al. [40] demonstrated the potential of LCA indicators for quantifying environmental, human health, and SDG impacts in energy transition scenarios, while Blanco et al. [6] applied ex-post LCA to estimate environmental impacts of Power-to-Methane systems using the JRC-EU-TIMES model. However, these studies reveal gaps in technical detail, particularly in lifecycle data for industries, such as Power-to-Liquid technologies [83], and face limitations in aligning with the more granular temporal and spatial resolution of ESMs.

From a methodological perspective, three main patterns for integrating LCA with IAMs/ESMs have emerged: (1) a process-based “cradle to grave” approach using LCA data, which often involves soft-linking the models [40,84]; (2) multiplying damage or economic factors from the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) database with inventories generated within the models through fully integrated, sometimes hard-linked approaches [7,85,86]; and (3) hybrid methods combining elements of both approaches [87]. However, many studies in this field, including those not referenced here, face challenges such as closed-source data, non-standardized assumptions, and difficulties in comparing results [82]. Common issues include double counting, regionalization, and high uncertainty in the data, compounded by limitations in the availability and quality of Lifecycle Inventory (LCI) data and LCIA analysis [82].

4.3. Barriers and issues to assess the role of LCFs in IAMs/ESMs

Insufficient model representation of LCFs. Increased interest in and potential commercialization of synthetic fuel technologies have yet to be covered in most IPCC IAMs and ESMs, particularly when contrasted with the extensive coverage of hydrogen production technologies. For future inclusion of synthetic fuel in energy system models, the presence of a variety of synfuel technologies and hydrogen production technologies as well as corresponding end-use applications should be ensured in the model to enable flexibility of the model to utilize these technologies. Additionally, they should be included along with other fuel conversion technologies instead of in isolation to assess their role in decarbonization in energy system models. Furthermore, the temporal resolution should be higher than annual to ensure that the intermittent nature of renewable electricity generation from wind and solar is reflected to support the production of hydrogen from electrolysis and synthetic fuels. Though some studies publish the techno-economic data used for the specific electrolyzer process, this is not always the case. Generalized electrolysis without specifying whether it is Alkaline Electrolysis cells (AEC), Polymer Electrolyte Membrane (PEM), or Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell (SOEC) process results in substantial cost deviations. Additionally, regarding technology learning rates, it is often unclear which specific technologies are assigned these rates and upon what source they are based. Despite the similar results in biofuel consumption in the ESMs, the sources of feedstock for biomass should be clear, whether it is lignocellulosic crops, forestry, wood waste, agricultural residues, or municipal solid wastes, to avoid an overestimation of resource potential.

Beyond the modeling of feedstock and technologies for synthetic

fuels, the representation of the end-use sectors can also introduce significant result deviations. The broader the range of applications powered by synthetic fuels within a model, the greater the potential contribution of these fuels to emission reductions. The way LCF applications are modeled plays a critical role in determining their importance and potential across different sectors and scenarios. As analyzed in Section 3.4, incomplete or limited modeling of LCF applications has led to many models underestimating the roles of hydrogen and biomass energy, particularly in sectors where these fuels could play a significant role in decarbonization efforts.

Finally, the results from the models do not explicitly indicate the proportion of electricity generated from renewable electricity nor differentiate the feedstocks of which the synthetic fuels have been consumed. Such opaqueness renders the revision of LCFs' roles difficult. Even though the IAM scenarios assessed are all net-zero 2050 scenarios, where an assumption can be made that all or at least the vast majority of electricity in the final year is generated by renewables or nuclear power, we cannot specify whether there is remaining fossil-fuel-based electricity with CCS and whether remaining GHG emissions are compensated for by CDR. The inability to determine the source of electricity leads directly to the inability to establish hydrogen as "green hydrogen" and hence evaluate and conclude regarding the contribution of e-fuels.

Lack of LCF EFs and environmental impact assessment in IAMs. One of the critical deficiencies in ESMs/IAMs concerning LCFs lies in their inadequate representation of environmental impact assessments, particularly with lifecycle EFs. While IAMs model GHG emissions based on activity levels and emission factors for energy systems, they often oversimplify or neglect the broader environmental trade-offs associated with LCFs. In terms of carbon accounting, many IAMs focus predominantly on direct emissions, particularly CO₂, and often overlook non-CO₂ GHG emissions, which can play a significant role in determining the overall environmental footprint of LCFs. Although progress has been made, the lack of comprehensive integration of LCA with IAMs/ESMs remains a critical research gap. To fully capture the role of LCFs in the energy system and to provide predictive analyses for future energy transitions, a more coherent and standardized framework is required. This would help address the spatial and temporal mismatches between LCAs and energy models, as well as the inconsistencies in data quality and representation.

Comparability between models and scenarios. Comparing different IAMs is inherently challenging. Although a range of studies [54,88] has developed diagnostic indicators to help describe how IAMs respond to climate policies, these indicators do not explain the connection with model-specific characteristics. Emission outcomes are more sensitive to IAM selection than to the assumed mitigation efforts. In our study, we focused on scenarios capable of achieving net-zero emissions and applied a series of filters to analyze IAMs' application patterns of LCFs from a structural perspective. However, this analysis remains largely qualitative. Quantitative correlation analyses are needed, requiring more explicit structural indicators, standardized scenario inputs and outputs, and data transparency.

The comparability of IAM scenarios also depends on the SSP settings covered by the IAMs and considerations of rapid technological advancements. Model versions also present an issue. During our data collection, mismatches between model versions and scenarios were observed. For example, some models in the IPCC database include historical versions but lack scenario data for the latest versions [1]. These newer versions have updated structures to incorporate technologies like hydrogen, but no further scenario results are provided. As with other model analyses [54,67], we considered the scenario results of the most recent versions. This approach has inherent inaccuracies, as models may include more detailed technological modeling or new fuel technologies in subsequent updates, but we cannot separate these details within unified scenarios.

The cross-comparison between ESMs and IAMs remains a necessary yet challenging endeavor. The primary distinctions between ESMs and

IAMs lie in their regional aggregation approaches, the focus areas of energy system modeling, and the granularity of demand-side details [89]. A recent study [90] compared the results of six IAMs and five ESMs across four core aspects of decarbonization scenarios within the EU: electricity generation, hydrogen production, the role of variable renewable energy sources, and nuclear power. The study indicated that IAMs employ a more aggregated methodology, while ESMs offer more detailed power sector modeling, corroborating our observations. Our research extends this comparison, providing a more detailed and diverse analysis. However, ESMs often simplify hydrogen demand-side modeling [90].

Comparing different models for the same region is inherently difficult, especially for smaller countries, as high regional aggregation can obscure local disparities. Another disconnection arises from the integration gap between IAMs' climate modules, other climate models, and ESMs. As demonstrated in Table 2, many climate module variations and other environmental impacts are not considered in ESMs, despite their critical implications for future energy systems. Enhancing collaboration between ESM and IAM modelers and establishing standardized regional and technical classifications could improve the comparability of model outcomes across various domains [91].

Differences between national/regional models and global models also warrant attention. As shown in Fig. 6, the selected regional models exhibit higher electricity usage and relatively higher LCF utilization. Typically, regional models offer fewer scenarios than global models. When comparing regional and global models for the same area under similar economic and population growth assumptions, discrepancies may arise in decarbonization targets, modeling methodologies, technological availability assumptions, and energy demand forecasts [20, 92]. Regional models often provide better regional specificity and higher resolution, while global models incorporate geopolitical and trade factors and unified climate change impact predictions.

4.4. Recommendations and future research

For future research on the role of LCFs in decarbonization, it is essential to comprehensively explore a variety of specific LCF technologies and their respective feedstock options, with particular emphasis on e-fuel production. Transparency in data sources and model structures is crucial to ensure the reliability and reproducibility of the findings. Additionally, end-use sectors should not be overlooked, as an increasing number of applications could integrate LCFs. Often neglected, but potentially significant sectors, include platform chemicals, shipping, international aviation, and road freight transport.

Enhancing both temporal and spatial resolutions would further improve the accuracy of modeling results for LCFs. Temporal resolution is particularly relevant given the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources used to produce low-carbon electricity. Meanwhile, spatial resolution is important for capturing regional resource potentials and, at a more granular level, the distances involved in transport and distribution. Moreover, depending on the specific research focus, it is vital to incorporate existing or proposed policies and regulations into models to reflect the projected development of LCFs. Examples include the ReFuel Aviation mandate or the implementation of carbon pricing on fuels.

The inclusion of more comprehensive LCA data is critical. A more holistic integration of LCA will allow for a full accounting of emissions and environmental impacts across the entire life cycle of LCFs—from resource extraction and production to transportation, use, and decommissioning. This will help to capture the indirect effects of LCF deployment, particularly land use changes and competition for resources. Detailed modeling of land-use impacts, including biofuel cultivation, renewable power and hydrogen infrastructure, and resource competition between food and fuel production, is essential to prevent unintended ecological consequences. Without such improvements, LCF strategies may inadvertently exacerbate environmental challenges rather than alleviate them.

In addition to lifecycle emissions, IAMs and ESMs need to address other GHG emissions beyond CO₂. Methane leaks from natural gas supply chains, nitrous oxide from bioenergy production, and the potential warming effects of hydrogen leaks, must be adequately considered in future models. These non-CO₂ emissions can significantly alter the overall climate impact of LCFs and need to be integrated into energy system models for more accurate scenario outcomes. The reliance on CO₂-centric modeling overlooks the broader scope of emissions and their diverse environmental impacts, limiting the effectiveness of LCF strategies in reducing total GHG emissions.

Our most important recommendations for future modeling efforts include.

- (1) **Improving transparency in data sources and scenario assumptions** by requiring that models clearly specify the technologies, feedstocks, and emissions factors used, along with their assumptions about future developments in technology and policy. This will allow for better comparison of model outcomes and scenario analyses, facilitating more robust conclusions.
- (2) **Incorporating high-resolution temporal and spatial data** in models to account for regional resource availability, variability in renewable energy production, and the dynamics of land use. Temporal resolution is particularly important for modeling the intermittency of renewable energy, which directly influences hydrogen and synthetic fuel production.
- (3) **Expanding the scope of end-use sectors and applications** for LCFs in IAMs and ESMs, such as shipping, aviation, and heavy industry. These sectors are harder to decarbonize, and their inclusion is vital to understanding the full potential of LCF technologies in achieving global climate targets.
- (4) **Developing standardized methods for emissions accounting** across LCF technologies, which should include both direct and indirect emissions. This would involve creating uniform criteria for assessing the lifecycle impacts of fuels and ensuring consistent treatment of technologies across different models.

Finally, ongoing collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders is necessary to ensure that modeling efforts remain aligned with real-world technological developments and policy shifts. Future research should explore the dynamic integration of emerging LCF technologies and policies into IAMs and ESMs, including carbon pricing mechanisms, renewable energy mandates, and advancements in CCS technologies. Additionally, more attention should be given to exploring the regional disparities in LCF deployment potential and how regional models can be better harmonized with global models.

5. Conclusions

This study critically assesses the role of low-carbon fuels (LCFs) in integrated assessment models (IAMs) and energy system models (ESMs), highlighting significant gaps and inconsistencies in their representation. While electrification is increasingly emphasized, other LCFs, such as hydrogen and liquid bioenergy, are pivotal for decarbonizing hard-to-electrify sectors, including heavy industry, transportation, and shipping—making them essential for achieving net-zero emissions. Our analysis reveals that the modeling of these comprehensive LCF portfolios within IAMs and ESMs remains fragmented, with substantial variability across models and scenarios.

The quantitative analysis underscores the importance of specific LCFs in different sectors and timeframes. By 2050, electrification accounts for 30–60 % of final energy demand in the most stringent climate scenarios (C1-C3), especially in models like REMIND and IMAGE. Hydrogen's role, though minimal in 2030, grows substantially by 2050, with shares reaching 6–8 % in sectors like industry and transportation, particularly in REMIND, TIAM, and IMAGE models. Liquid bioenergy, while prominent in the transportation sector, remains highly variable,

with COFFEE showing the highest shares, reaching up to 30 % in certain scenarios. This variation underscores the different assumptions regarding LCF deployment and their implications for achieving net-zero targets.

Our review also identifies a significant lack of standardization in how LCFs are defined, categorized, and applied across sectors. This inconsistency, particularly in transportation, industry, and residential sectors, hinders the models' capacity to fully represent the role of LCFs. Additionally, critical environmental considerations, such as non-CO₂ emissions (e.g., methane and hydrogen leaks from hydrogen production and biofuel supply chains) and land-use impacts from large-scale bioenergy, are frequently underrepresented or overlooked, distorting the evaluation of LCFs' true environmental benefits. This limits the ability to generate accurate decarbonization pathways that can guide sustainable policy decisions.

To address these gaps, enhancing both temporal and spatial model resolution is crucial, particularly for capturing the dynamic integration of intermittent renewable energy sources that are essential for hydrogen and synthetic fuel production. Models should also incorporate detailed LCA and EFs to better account for the environmental impacts of LCFs beyond CO₂ emissions. This would allow for a more comprehensive assessment of the trade-offs between different technologies and LCFs, leading to more robust decarbonization strategies.

A key limitation of this review is that it does not fully capture the most recent scenario developments or ongoing modeling efforts, which continue to evolve. Additionally, while this study focuses on electrification, hydrogen, synfuels and bioenergy in the scenario result analysis, other emerging LCFs—such as green ammonia, methane pyrolysis hydrogen, sun-to-liquid fuels—are not comprehensively represented in current models, particularly in sectoral end-use applications like aviation and shipping. Future work should prioritize integrating these LCFs across models to provide a more holistic picture of decarbonization options.

In conclusion, LCFs hold immense promise for contributing to global decarbonization, but their full potential can only be realized if current modeling frameworks are refined. Standardizing the classification of LCFs, integrating comprehensive LCA data, and expanding scenario designs will be critical for generating reliable, policy-relevant insights into net-zero emission pathways. By advancing these areas, IAMs and ESMs can serve as more effective tools for guiding the deployment of sustainable, low-carbon fuels, ensuring that global climate goals are met through scientifically grounded strategies.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zipeng Liu: Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Meixi Zhang:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Christian Bauer:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Russell McKenna:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.115608>.

Data availability

The data of Figs. 4-6 can be found in the supplementary Excel file. Further data from this study can be found in the supplementary information and the references.

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